

Traco DC/DC converter: Vout analysis

1. Goal

Have a stable power supply of 5V for raspberry pi and colibrys sensors.

2. Setup 1

3. Setup 2

4. Setup 3 (10 μ F, 100nF capacitors in parallel)

5. Setup 4 (Measuring Bandwidth 20 MHz)

